
A guide for Country Representative Council Members of the European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA) initiative: Roles & Responsibilities as Community Representatives

Developed by the ERGA Executive Board and the ERGA Council
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Country Representative ERGA Council Members

The ERGA Members of each country are asked to nominate up to two ERGA Members to represent them on the ERGA Council. These positions on the Council may be renewed or replaced according to the decisions made within each country. Please refer to the [ERGA Governance](#) for further information, definitions, and procedures.

Country Representative Roles

Country representative Council Members form part of the ERGA Council, the operational governing body responsible for representing all European countries involved in ERGA and, thereby, all ERGA Members. As Council Members, the role of country representatives is to participate in Council activities, discussing, debating, and voting on important decisions that shape the structure, goals, and priorities of ERGA, primarily through joining the monthly online ERGA Council meetings.

Country Representative Responsibilities

All ERGA Council Members are volunteers; it is, therefore, normal to expect different levels of engagement and participation throughout the year, e.g. during periods with heavy teaching or with fieldwork activities. Nevertheless, Council Members are asked to consider the following responsibilities as important aspects of their positions:

- Attend and actively **contribute to ERGA Council meetings**, as they serve as the primary forum for all debate and decision-making regarding ERGA's governance, structure, goals, vision, policies, and key initiatives. If you are unable to attend a Council meeting, please indicate your apologies in the agenda ahead of the meeting and designate a named substitute to attend on your behalf. The aim is to have every country represented at Council meetings, so if no country representative can attend it is important to identify a suitable substitute for your country if possible.
- Represent your country's perspectives** within ERGA, ensuring as far as possible that they reflect those of your country members, even when there is no consensus position/perspective. This is a two-way conversation, keeping your country members up to date with key information and listening to your country members to bring their questions for discussion at Council meetings.

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- Engage with and **participate in voting procedures** on decisions that shape the organisation and direction of ERGA. This means participating in the discussions before any vote - asking questions, seeking the opinions of your country members if deemed necessary, expressing points of view - also reading any materials provided regarding the topic under discussion, and finally, making sure to cast your votes when an electronic vote is carried out. We need widespread participation to ensure that the decisions we make are truly reflective of the community we serve.
 - Ensure that your **country representatives are reviewed** at least annually, allowing for the possibility of renewal or replacement. The review process and selection of representatives are decided within each country, the recommendation is to strive for diversity in this representation, e.g., from different institutions or regions of a country.

Additional activities that country representatives could consider promoting that would help you fulfil the responsibilities outlined above include but are not limited to:

- Setting up and using a country-level mailing list is a good way for national discussions and information sharing, allowing you to properly represent your country members. This can be seen as a first step towards creating a National ERGA Node in your country.
- Maintaining active, regular, and fruitful communications with your fellow country representatives greatly helps to improve the coordination of activities within your country and enhances the representatives' ability to understand country needs.
- Engaging with your country members by organising national meetings helps to promote collaboration and discussion on relevant researcher needs, research lines, and funding opportunities - these can be informal meetings, e.g., attached to national conferences.
- Engaging with ERGA Committees periodically on topics relevant to your country's research agenda (e.g., permits, Nagoya Protocol) helps to bring key subjects to the attention of the Committees to seek common solutions and benefit all ERGA Members.
- Including in your presentations one or two slides about ERGA in your language and sharing these slides with your country members contributes to disseminating ERGA's mission in your country. The ERGA Media Committee can support you with this.
- Sharing announcements of ERGA-related events with your country members and sharing information about events in your country with the wider ERGA membership encourages participation, particularly amongst early career scientists.
- Organising *ad hoc* meetings with the ERGA Executive Board to discuss your past, ongoing, and future work as country representatives is often a very useful exercise to share experiences and better understand how we collectively serve our community.